

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING PR-ADVERTISING SERVICES IN THE PROCESS OF PRODUCT DELIVERY ON THE EXAMPLE OF BUKHARA REGION

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Abstract. This article describes the indicators of the effectiveness of using PR-advertising services in the process of product delivery, the advantages of consumer organizations, the specific characteristics of the methods of studying consumer preferences, recommendations for determining and developing the level of loyalty of residents and entrepreneurs of the Bukhara region.

Key words: market, economic system, consumer, producer, SMM agency, commercial activity, marketing research, NPS, behavioral motives, field research.

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ УСЛУГ PR-РЕКЛАМЫ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ДОСТАВКИ ПРОДУКЦИИ НА ПРИМЕРЕ БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

Аннотация. В статье описаны показатели эффективности использования PR-рекламных услуг в процессе доставки продукции, преимущества потребительских организаций, особенности методов изучения потребительских предпочтений, рекомендации по определению и развитию уровня лояльности жители и предприниматели Бухарской области.

Ключевые слова: рынок, экономическая система, потребитель, производитель, SMM-агентство, коммерческая деятельность, маркетинговые исследования, NPS, поведенческие мотивы, полевые исследования.

Market economic system is the main form of economic life of modern society. The concept of market is a basic concept in the theory of market economy.

The market is a consumer-oriented economic system. This explains the constant interest of economic science in how an ordinary consumer behaves, what motives and rules he follows when choosing a large assortment of goods, the existence of laws regulating his behavior in the market, and methods of stimulation. At present, the relationship between the consumer and the producer is built in such a way that the consumer is at the center of the producer's interests and is his main goal and the object of targeted influence. Therefore, it is important for the manufacturer to study the preferences of consumers from a psychological, economic, sociological and cultural point of view.

Studying the preferences of consumer organizations is the most important element of the commercial activity of any SMM agency.¹ Customers are at the heart of any successful business, regardless of the size of the operation. Studying consumers, their wishes and preferences allows the SMM agency to offer them exactly what they need.

¹ <https://topagency.com/glossary/social-media-marketing-agency-definition/#:~:text=marketing%20agencies%20work-,Strategy,to%20reach%20their%20target%20markets.>

The main task in the study of consumer organizations is to determine the factors influencing their behavior. In order to successfully operate in the services market, the SMM agency needs to make timely changes to the product (service) itself, optimize advertising channels and advertising strategy, i.e. adapt all components of the marketing mix to changes in consumer preferences. should know in advance. .

Marketing research on consumer preferences focuses on understanding behavioral motivations and identifying consumer values. The main purpose of conducting such research is to reduce the level of uncertainty in making certain management decisions. The main tasks of marketing research of consumer preferences are to identify potential and current market opportunities, to identify competitors, to study the dynamics of the shares of the main participants in the market, to create and analyze a portrait of consumer organizations.

Table 1.

Peculiarities of methods of studying consumer preferences.

Method	Feature of the method
Lichnoe interview	Direct communication between the interviewer and the respondent. Allows you to get answers to questions of increased complexity. During a personal interview, the interviewer can interest the respondent, establish the best possible contact with him, and reduce the likelihood of refusal to answer.
Telephone interview	The most economical method of data collection (low cost). The survey can be completed fairly quickly. The data obtained from the respondent using this method is entered into the database during the conversation with him.
Electronic survey	Filling out the questionnaire takes less time, and respondents can think about and weigh the questions. Checking the entered values, monitoring the mandatory completion of questions. Demonstration of video and audio materials, as well as images of any format. Low costs.
Glubinnoe interview	Allows you to obtain non-formalized information of a qualitative nature. Study of hard-to-reach respondents (high-income individuals).
Focus group	The conversation is conducted in a relaxed atmosphere. Opportunity to express your opinion honestly and freely. It is possible to demonstrate the product, its taste, smell and other properties. During the discussion, advantages and disadvantages that were previously hidden can be discovered.

1. The level of loyalty of residents and entrepreneurs of the Bukhara region can be determined using one of the loyalty measurement methods. In this case, the traditional method is used. A survey to evaluate the NPS of Bukhara region entrepreneurs.

2. NPS (NetPromoterScore)² is an index showing customer loyalty to a brand, product, or service.

3. Measuring the NPS loyalty index includes 3 steps:

4. The consumer answers the question "How likely are you to recommend the company/product/service to your acquaintances, friends, colleagues?" In this case, it is suggested that the rating be made on a 10-point scale, where 10 is "I definitely recommend", 0 is "I do not recommend under any circumstances."

5. According to the received ratings, consumers are divided into 3 groups: 10-9 points - brand/product supporters, 8-7 points - neutral consumers, 6-0 points - critics.

6. The calculation of the consumer loyalty index itself is determined using the NPS³ formula=
$$\left(\frac{\text{Number of supporters}}{\text{Total number of respondents}} \right) - \left(\frac{\text{Number of critics}}{\text{Total number of respondents}} \right).$$

The respondent chooses a number from 0 to 10, thereby indicating which extreme point he belongs to. The sample includes 30 people. The results of the questionnaire are summarized in the table.

The primary data collection methods in field research are: observation, experiment (test), survey. Advantages of field research:

- provide more information than other research methods;
- to provide the researcher with more flexibility compared to other research methods;
- field research is more likely to reveal unexpected results than other methods.

A plan to study the preferences of consumers in the market of fast food restaurant services on the example of Bukhara region:

- 1) questionnaire;
- 2) observation;
- 3) targeted interview (focus group).

The questionnaire survey method was chosen because of its versatility, efficiency and cost. The target population of this study was selected based on the geographic segmentation of the market. A sample of 20 people was taken from all clients of the agency. Sample participants were given questionnaires consisting of a list of 18 multiple-choice control questions. For each question, you can choose the answer option that is most suitable for the respondent. Sample questionnaire used for this study.

The data obtained after the survey is presented below, including in graphical form.

Respondents indicated their annual income - for most it is more than 25 million soums.

² [https://www.qualtrics.com/experience-management/customer/net-promoter-score/#:~:text=Net%20Promoter%20Score%20\(NPS\)%20definition,a%20higher%20score%20is%20desirable.](https://www.qualtrics.com/experience-management/customer/net-promoter-score/#:~:text=Net%20Promoter%20Score%20(NPS)%20definition,a%20higher%20score%20is%20desirable.)

³ [https://www.qualtrics.com/experience-management/customer/net-promoter-score/#:~:text=Net%20Promoter%20Score%20\(NPS\)%20definition,a%20higher%20score%20is%20desirable.](https://www.qualtrics.com/experience-management/customer/net-promoter-score/#:~:text=Net%20Promoter%20Score%20(NPS)%20definition,a%20higher%20score%20is%20desirable.)

Annual income of respondents, million soums.

When choosing an agency, the respondent is guided by the quality of the services offered. However, cost and methods do not have as much influence on consumer choice.

Factors affecting consumers' choice of products of entrepreneurs of Bukhara region

In conclusion, it can be said that we made the following comments.

1) Most of the respondents are neutral consumers.

Neutral consumers are consumers who are not loyal to a particular agency, but do not harm the company's reputation.

2) Supporters of the company make up 30% of the total number of supporters.

Company supporters/allies are a category of consumers who recommend the company to the environment. Such customers are the most valuable for the company. They often make purchases from this company, and the life cycle of such customers is of the utmost importance.

3) Critics occupy the smallest part of the total number of survey participants.

This is part of the customers who are not satisfied with our service and service delivery. They want to destroy your reputation by spreading negative reviews.

$$NPS = \left(\frac{\text{Number of supporters}}{\text{Total number of respondents}} \right) - \left(\frac{\text{Number of critics}}{\text{Total number of respondents}} \right)$$

$$NPS = \left(\frac{9}{30} \right) - \left(\frac{5}{30} \right) \times 100\% = 34\%.$$

Based on the above, we can conclude that the NPS loyalty index = 34%, which means a good result of loyalty programs.

Retail audit is monitoring changes in various product indicators (price, assortment, level of representation in retail outlets, variety of packaging, sales volume) in the changing market situation and taking into account the activities of competitors. Retail audit information includes obtaining a database of market operators (by manufacturers, product categories, brands), determining the

market structure of the studied product, conducting a comparative analysis of pricing policy, assortment policy, advertising activities and distribution. allows to analyze the indicators. the main participants of the studied product market and others.

The main purpose of the observation within the framework of this project is to study the actions of enterprises when concluding an agreement with the agency. It was decided to monitor:

- range of services;
- prices;
- consumer behavior when choosing and ordering services.

The agency is working on customer loyalty, but it should work more and turn neutral customers into customers from which only entrepreneurs of the Bukhara region order services.

High customer loyalty to the agency is very necessary, because the growth of profits and the success of the company as a whole depends on it.

Recommendations aimed at increasing the loyalty of consumer organizations on the example of Bukhara region include:

1. Increased customer life cycle.

Most of the clients are satisfied with the company's service. That is why it is very important to keep in constant contact with the clients and thereby increase the possibility of returning to the agency.

2. Work with your employees, control training and communication with customers.

Some employees may not finish working with the client, this should be prevented and constantly monitored. Equally important is developing loyalty among subordinates. A warm attitude in the team will never harm customers, but only encourage warm communication between these channels.

3. The main thing is to improve your services based on the recommendations of the target audience, and not on your own images.

4. Honesty with customers. This rule should be taken as a value and should not be deviated from. If something is promised, it must be fulfilled.

5. Monitoring of the ongoing activity is carried out using various methods. Thanks to services such as Yandex Metrica, which allows you to monitor website traffic in real time, you can adjust the ongoing activity during business hours, find the most effective means of communication, analyze demand and adapt to customer needs in time.

In addition to the above, we can conclude that this company has a growth trend. In order to maintain this pace, it is necessary to control the improvement of the quality of the provided services, increase the qualification of personnel and improve the technical base.

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